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Saltmarsh Ecosystems as Nature-Based Solutions for Water Quality Management and Climate Resilience: A Case Study from the Lima Estuary

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Saltmarshes are productive ecosystems located at the land-sea interface along sheltered coastlines, providing a diverse range of critical ecosystem services and goods and benefits for society. These include coastal and flood protection, biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, food provision, and water purification, among others. Despite their importance, these ecosystems have been subjected to significant degradation due to human activities. Natural wetlands, including saltmarshes, are increasingly recognized as nature-based solutions (NBS) in water management strategies, particularly in regulating the hydrological cycle and improving water quality. Estuarine saltmarshes can help remove organic and inorganic contaminants from surface waters, thereby mitigating the effects of wastewater and other diffuse sources of pollution. In the Lima estuary (northern Portugal), an innovative approach is being implemented that combines the phytoremediation potential of saltmarsh halophytes with pilot revegetation efforts to enhance the uptake and/or biodegradation of contaminants present in sediment and surface water. The saltmarsh's role in mitigating saltwater intrusion and coastal erosion during extreme weather events, under various climate change scenarios, is also being assessed using ecosystem services models. Furthermore, a multi-stakeholder livinglab has been established to raise awareness of the importance of saltmarshes as NBS, aiming to foster community engagement through co-designed activities for the protection of these ecosystems. All these activities are being developed the framework of the Mar2Protect EU project, to showcase the potential of saltmarsh ecosystems in promoting sustainable water management and climate adaptation.

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